

Off-axis microDoppler imaging of blood flow for ophthalmology

Internship proposal

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Mission : The students will contribute to the development of a microDoppler holography device prototype for blood flow imaging in capillary retinal vessels. Their tasks will encompass optical interferometer design, wave-based coherent image formation, fluctuation analysis, statistical filtering, and digital correction of optical aberrations. Signal processing will be prototyped in Matlab. All developed routines will be shared via [GitHub](#) for collaborative use and further enhancement.

Value proposition : Building on the success of Doppler holography for ophthalmology [[Fischer 2024](#)], now deployed in selected prestigious clinical research centers globally, this project aims to develop a real-time microDoppler holography retinal imaging device for clinical use. It will enable blood flow imaging in capillary vessels in the anterior and posterior segments of the eye, enhancing the spatial resolution of Doppler holography. Unlike optical coherence tomographic angiography (OCT-A), which only allows for a quasi-static mapping of retinal capillaries, this technology will offer dynamic imaging in small retinal vessels and is designed for large-scale clinical use.

Fig. time-domain holographic OCT of the eye fundus [[Sudkamp 2016](#)] (left). Quantitative Doppler holography of retinal blood flow [[Fischer 2024](#)] (right).

Proposed device : This project aims at investigating instrumental approaches for functional blood flow imaging in retinal capillaries, leveraging cutting-edge technologies: time-domain OCT [[Sudkamp 2016](#)] and Doppler holography [[Fischer 2024](#)]. An imaging device for the human retina will be developed, combining various temporal coherence laser light sources with holographic detection via a camera with a Mach Zehnder

interferometer. Digital image reconstruction and filtering utilizing singular value decomposition will enhance the detection of off-axis interference signals .

Instrumental approach and technological development : The light source, operating in the near-infrared range, will be either a superluminescent or a laser diode. The light beam will be used for time-domain holographic OCT of the eye fundus [Sudkamp 2016], via off-axis interferometry; Optical interference patterns will be captured by an ultra-fast streaming camera, up to 33,000 frames per second [Fischer 2024]. These interference patterns will arise from the interaction between the defocused image of the retina and the reference wave. Singular value decomposition will be leveraged for revealing the on-axis interference signal, and filter-out artifacts such as self-beating signals and overlapping ghost images [Puyo 2020]. Temporal analysis will uncover retinal dynamics in cross-sectional images with slice thickness matching the retina depth, allowing Doppler holography of blood flow in microvessels with acquisition speeds at least 100 times faster than current camera-based swept-source OCTA [Liżewski 2024].

Rationale : Doppler holography enables dynamic blood flow measurements with excellent temporal resolution, high repeatability, and the ability to assess total retinal blood volume rate in major vessels [Fischer 2024]. Already used in longitudinal studies, this clinical-grade technology will now be advanced to higher-resolution **microDoppler** angiography, focusing on capillary retinal plexuses. This robust technology will offer key advantages for clinical applications :

- **Ocular safety compliance**: The use of a diffuser to broaden the focal point of illumination in front of the eyepiece will be investigated to ensure ocular safety compliance while preserving high imaging fidelity.
- **Digital aberration correction**: This system will integrate digital aberration compensation for high-resolution imaging that is also already performed for Doppler holography [Bratasz 2024], eliminating the need for physical aberration compensation systems, which are ineffective for patients lacking suitable anterior segment conditions, and hence improving massively clinical relevance.

State-of-the-art STOC-T OCTA angiography analyzes fluctuations in successive swept-source OCT volumes, with a repetition rate of 113 Hz [Liżewski 2024], while cutting-edge methods like VISTA OCTA achieve 1000 Hz [Hwang 2023]. Clinical-grade **microDoppler** holography will reach up to 37,000 Hz en-face time-domain OCT in real-time by using a short-coherence laser and a fast streaming camera. This will open the way to high temporal resolution imaging of the whole retina, crucial for capillary blood flow imaging. Some depth sectioning within the retina will be achieved through digital refocusing in post-processing, which will also crucially allow axial image registration. The retina contains up to four vascular networks: the superficial vascular plexus, two deeper capillary

plexuses, and the radial peripapillary plexus [Campbell 2017], the deep ones being difficult to image with fluorescein angiography. The near-infrared transparency of the retina makes it ideal for digital holographic imaging. By trading volumetric depth sectioning for much higher temporal resolution, **microDoppler** will enable high-resolution imaging of blood flow in the capillary networks, offering better insight into conditions like glaucoma and diabetic retinopathy, which are linked to microvascular impairment. This device will provide :

- **Real-time blood flow monitoring:** The high temporal resolution, capturing tens of thousands of images per second, will enable detailed real-time analysis of blood flow dynamics in microcapillaries using [Holovibes](#), the leading open-source software for high-throughput, low-latency digital hologram rendering and fluctuation analysis. It is already used for real-time Doppler holography clinical research worldwide.
- **True clinical utility:** This technology will deliver a clinical-grade imaging system for detailed hemodynamic analysis in retinal microvessels, offering unmatched speed, precision, and ease in practical settings. A laser with appropriate coherence length will enable full-depth retina imaging, while motion registration will be handled in post-processing for scalable clinical use.

References :

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